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A CHANGE IN BEHAVIOR OF BANKING SECTOR FOR MICRO FINANCE IN MSME

Mayank Singhal

Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Institute, Modinagar, Ghaziabad

Main Market Muradnagar, Ghaziabad,

Abstract

The setting of interest rates in the field of microfinance (MF) has been hotly debated for years. On the one hand, it is claimed that high interest rates are justified because of the elevated operating and processing costs of serving very small loans without collateral. Today India has just slowdown in unemployment. Through this research paper we have just disclosed the India banking structure change of Micro finance. In 2011 India launched a cap on MF interest rates of 26% for loans up to 50,000 rupees (US\$1,124) and at that rate stagnation and reduced borrowing followed. To offset this, in April 2014, the Reserve Bank of India introduced a more flexible rate: cost of funds (at market rates) plus 10% for existing MFIs and cost of funds plus 12% for new MFIs. A recent study by CGAP (Consultative Group to Assist the Poor) analyzed interest rates in over 866 MFIs between 2004 and 2011, finding that most African countries have instituted interest rate caps to protect consumers, in some cases due to political and cultural pressures.

Key words: Interest rate, micro finance, Banking structure, CGAP, micro finance institutions.

Introduction

Microfinance is a source of financial service for entrepreneurs and small businesses that enables the poor to pull themselves out of poverty. For some, microfinance is a movement whose object is "a world in which as many poor and near-poor households as possible have permanent access to an appropriate range of high quality financial services, including not just credit but also savings, insurance, and fund transfers."^[1] Many of those who promote microfinance generally believe that such access will help poor people out of poverty, including participants in the Microcredit Summit Campaign. Most commonly, it involves making small loans to the working poor in developing countries. These loans are usually less than \$200 and are made by local organizations called microfinance institutions.

How Micro Finance Works

Credit refers to programs that primarily provide credit in tiny amounts for self-employment but also other financial and business services to very poor persons, mainly women. It reflects the fact that thousands of microfinance institutions of varying structure, degree of

The power of compound interest will result in unpaid loans leaving the lender and the borrower in distress. The result is a vicious cycle that sets up a domino effect of defaulters. Compounding interest grows so fast and the borrower would not be able to pay his bank dues making the economy to pay the price. So, charging interest may not be a solution for financing MSEs at least for those disadvantaged (SC/ST/OBCs) and those at the lower end of the spectrum.

According to experts in finance, conventional finance creates artificial money supply not being backed by real assets leading to high inflation, rich becoming richer. So, what is the solution available for financing such assets of MSEs which are run by those who do not have means to offer even collaterals, particularly the enterprises set up by SC/ST/OBCs. Therefore, the strategy proposed will be a combination of providing investment finance by way of 'finance lease' in lieu of term loan and /or using 'participative financing'. In addition, an outline on the idea of introduction of 'Referral Programmes for MSE customers' is also given in the paper.

Introduce Referral Programmes

'Referral Programmes' are popular among a number of new generation industries, particularly the IT sector. On similar lines, banks may consider introducing 'Referral Programmes' for getting new MSE customers. They can use their existing customers running an MSE as 'Referral Ambassadors' by providing suitable incentives/ rewards to them.

Running an incentive programme to reward such 'ambassadors for referrals' is a time tested method of dramatically increasing 'word of mouth' (WOM) success. The referral/ reward structure taps into an innate desire to help others. Such programmes present a lot of room for creativity in the structure, cost and development of referral incentives.

In developing a suitable reward structure for referral ambassadors, banks should keep in view that the incentive should be enough to interest the customers to participate and it should not erase the profit of the new revenue generated. So, the first step in determining the 'optimum incentive value cost' is to analyse the 'Customer Lifetime Value' (CLV) and 'Customer Acquisition Cost' (CAC). These two concepts are extremely important for banks looking to get a good ROI on their marketing investment[6]. Rewards can be either monetary or non-monetary or a combination of both.

The idea of introducing referral programmes among banks for promoting MSEs needs policy support from the RBI. Hence, details and modalities of a suitable incentive/reward structure have not been attempted in this paper.

Conclusion:

Access to financial services has been proven to be a powerful tool to help fight poverty.

The impact is greatest especially for the poor people when they have access to a broad range of financial services with which they can invest in income generating and asset building activities to meet basic needs such as health, education and nutrition. The ability to manage assets helps poor people to gain control of their own future and make greater contribution to national development. India like any other developing country is saddled with the problem of rural-urban migration, mass illiteracy, poor infrastructural facilities, poverty and low access to formal financial services. This requires a vibrant micro finance initiative aimed at expanding the financial infrastructure of the country to meet the financial requirements of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMES) as well as the need of the rural and urban poor. For the country's economically active poor to rise above their current poverty level, the micro finance banks must be seen to be up and doing as this is the only way they can achieve their mandate and true purpose of their existence.

To date, the objective of microenterprise development has driven much of the microfinance field. While microenterprises are an important source of income for many poor households, they are only one part of their overall livelihood systems. Microfinance is more than credit, and as shown in this research, microfinance can play an important role beyond enterprise development in supporting the livelihoods of the poor. The concept of livelihood is a broader concept than that of enterprise development. It considers a mix of resources, activities, and capabilities that enable individuals and households to pursue their economic goals. In reality, resources within households are fungible, and it is important to recognise that clients will use microfinance services for a variety of purposes. Clients use microfinance not only to invest in enterprises, but also to build household assets, smooth income, and help manage their cash flow. By providing chunks of money when it is needed, microfinance can help clients reduce their vulnerability, expand their options, and graduate from a reactive mode of survival to a proactive climb out of poverty.

References

1. Robert Peck Christen, Richard Rosenberg & Veena Jayadeva. *Financial institutions with a double-bottom line: implications for the future of microfinance*. CGAP Occasional Paper, July 2004, pp. 2-3
2. Address by Shri Anand Sinha, Deputy Governor, RBI, at the National Conference on Enhancing Competitiveness with MSME linkages, organised by the Indian Chamber of Commerce, Kolkata, July 12, 2012.
3. Ibid
4. Report of the Working Group to Review the CGTMSE, RBI, March, 2010.